

TO THE QUESTION OF CHOOSING THE RESEARCH OBJECT ON THE TOPIC OF NOOTROPIC DRUGS

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17326318>

Relevance: Nootropic drugs occupy a key place in modern neurological and psychiatric practice, as they help improve cognitive functions, memory recovery, concentration, and neuroplasticity. Their use is particularly relevant in the rehabilitation of patients after serious meningitis, traumatic brain injuries, strokes, and other neuroinfections accompanied by cognitive impairments. According to DRUG-audit data for 2022–2024, the Republic of Uzbekistan has witnessed not only a steady increase in sales of nootropic drugs but also an expansion of their therapeutic applications. The share of nootropics in the psychoanaleptic drug segment consistently exceeds 85% of the total pharmaceutical market in this category. The greatest interest is shown in drugs with the International Nonproprietary Names (INN) - Piracetam, Citicoline, Hopantenic acid, and Meclofenoxate - which demonstrate high prescription rates, proven efficacy, and favorable clinical outcomes. Additionally, pharmacoeconomic factors such as the affordability of drugs for different population groups and their inclusion in therapy standards are taken into account.

Research Objective: To determine the optimal object for subsequent pharmacological and clinical studies among nootropic drugs, taking into account DRUG-audit data, INNs, clinical efficacy indicators, safety profiles, and economic feasibility.

Materials and Methods: The study included a comprehensive analysis of DRUG-audit statistical data covering sales volumes, consumption dynamics, and price segments of nootropic drugs for 2022–2024. Comparative analysis methods were additionally used to evaluate pharmacological properties, safety profiles, and frequency of clinical use of drugs with different INNs. To enhance objectivity, information from international databases and recommendations from clinical protocols on the use of nootropics in neurorehabilitation were also utilized.

Results: According to DRUG-audit data, drugs with the INNs Piracetam and Citicoline consistently hold leading positions in terms of sales volumes and prescription frequency, accounting for over 40% of the entire nootropic drug market. Drugs with the INNs Hopantenic acid and Meclofenoxate, although occupying a smaller market share, demonstrate a steady positive trend due to their active use in the rehabilitation of patients after neurological diseases and in pediatric practice.

Conclusions: Based on a comprehensive analysis, drugs with the INNs Citicoline and Hopantenic acid can be recommended for further pharmacological and clinical studies. They possess proven clinical efficacy, pronounced neuroprotective effects, acceptable safety profiles, and high usage frequency in real-world medical practice. The use of DRUG-audit data in combination with INN analysis and pharmacoeconomic factors makes it possible to justify the choice of the research object not only from a clinical but also from an economic and social perspective. This is an important aspect for developing a rational pharmacotherapy strategy for cognitive disorders and rehabilitation of patients with neurological pathology.